

SIMULATION OF RESIN INFUSION IN THE MANUFACTURE OF FIBER METAL LAMINATES BY VARTM

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1 Introduction

NASA Langley Research Center has developed a process for the manufacture of fiber metal laminates (FMLs) by vacuum assisted resin transfer molding VARTM [1,2]. A hybrid preform is created by stacking alternating layers of the metal sheets and dry woven fabrics. The preform is placed on the tool and bagged as shown in Figure 1. Resin is infused into the dry woven fabrics and will bond the metal sheets to the reinforcing fiber layers when cured. A distribution medium is commonly incorporated on top of the lay up to enhance the resin infiltration process. This variation of the VARTM process is known as the SCRIMP[®] process [3,4]. With the addition of the highly permeable distribution medium, resin rapidly flows over the surface of the part and is infused into the hybrid preform by the pressure difference created by the vacuum source. Since resin flow is primarily in the through-the-thickness or transverse direction, resin pathways must be inserted into the metal sheets to allow resin to infiltrate into the dry woven fabric (Figure 1). The size and shape of the pathways must be large enough to permit resin to flow into and wet-out the woven fabrics, but small enough as to minimize any compromise to the structural performance of the FML.

The objective of this investigation was to develop and verify a simulation model of resin infusion in the manufacture of fiber metal laminates by the VARTM process.

2 Simulation Model

A three dimensional model was developed using the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software FLUENT to simulate the VARTM FML infiltration

process. The resin flow was modeled as a two-phase fluid flow through the porous medium. A multiphase volume of fluid (VOF) model [5] was adopted to track the resin flow patterns and an Euler explicit

Fig. 1. Diagram of the FML VARTM process

time-dependent formulation was used for the solution of the VOF scheme.

During resin infusion, flow is only in the transverse direction through the flow pathways that have been machined into the metal sheets. A large number of pathways exist in each layer and they typically have very small diameters compared to the planar dimensions of the preforms. In addition, the overall thicknesses of the preforms used in the FML structures are also typically much smaller compared to the planar dimensions. This brings a potential problem of divergence in the flow solution due to the high aspect ratios of the mesh cells and also the computational burden of using an extremely fine mesh around the small diameter pathways. In order to generate a more stable and simplified model, each row of pathways along the length of the metal sheets was modeled as a *porous strip* of width equal to the diameter of the pathways and with an equivalent

permeability. An example of the porous strips is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Flow pathways modeled as porous strips.

Obviously, the size and number of the porous strips depends on the geometry of the hybrid preform and diameter of the flow pathways. The number of flow pathways in the porous strip is accounted for by the effective permeability.

The porous strips were modeled using the “porous jump” boundary condition in FLUENT. Porous jump conditions are used to model thin membranes with known velocity (pressure-drop) characteristics [6]. It is essentially a one-dimensional simplification of the porous medium model available for cell zones. This simpler model is more robust and yields better convergence.

The 3D geometry of the hybrid preform was generated using GAMBIT. GAMBIT is a preprocessor program for FLUENT used to build and mesh the models. The glass fabrics and distribution medium were modeled as three dimensional porous volumes and the flow pathways were modeled as a series of parallel porous strips. A single 3D volume element was placed in the thickness direction of each layer of reinforcement. A single 3D volume was placed in the thickness direction for the entire distribution medium, which included multiple layers of the LDPE/HDPE fabric. Porous strips representing the flow pathways in the metal sheets were modeled as two dimensional

shared surfaces between two consecutive layers of the reinforcement or between one layer of reinforcement and the distribution medium. In this way, each layer of reinforcement, except the one at the very bottom, had porous strips both at the top and bottom surfaces. The distribution medium had porous strips only at the bottom surface, which were also shared by the top layer of reinforcement. For the 35.56 cm long by 35.56 cm wide hybrid preforms used in the model verification experiment, the flow pathways in each metal sheet were represented by 27 parallel porous strips for the 1.27 cm spacing. In order to include the effect of race-tracking along the edges of the mold, two channels, each 4 mm wide, were included in the model.

A three dimensional mesh of the overall geometry is shown in Figure 3. The distribution medium (pink) is shown on the top and the fabric preform (green) is shown at the bottom. The injection port is shown to the right.

Fig. 3. Three dimensional mesh created in GAMBIT

The boundary conditions are defined as follows. The resin injection port was modeled as a square pressure inlet, which has the same cross sectional area as the circular injection port used in the tests. This was done to preserve the uniformity of the mesh composed of hexahedral cells and to avoid long computation times. A “pressure inlet” boundary condition was defined at the injection port. All the top and side surfaces of the distribution medium were defined as “wall”, except for the left end face which was defined as “pressure outlet” to allow flow of resin into the hybrid preform. “Pressure outlet” boundary conditions were specified at the left-end

(resin outlet side) of the race-tracking channels and the preform. The side faces of the glass preform, modeled as race-tracking channels, were defined as an “interior boundary” to allow the flow of resin into these channels.

After the boundary conditions were assigned in GAMBIT, the three dimensional mesh was exported to FLUENT for further processing and calculation. In FLUENT, pressure inlet and outlet conditions, operating conditions, material properties, initial conditions of the phases and porous jump conditions were defined. Additional details of the simulation model can be found in Reference 7.

3 Experimental

The hybrid preform was formed by stacking alternating layers of treated and primed 2024-T3 aluminum sheets, 0.381 mm thick and eight-harness satin weave S-glass fabrics (see Figure 1). The hybrid preform consisted of five layers of aluminum sheet and four layers of S-glass fabric. The flow pathways were drilled into the aluminum sheets with a diameter d of 0.41 mm and a spacing S of 1.27 cm as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Flow pathway spacing and diameter.

The hybrid preform was placed on a steel tool, vacuum bagged and infused with Applied Poleramic SC-85 epoxy using the Controlled Atmospheric Pressure Resin Infusion (CAPRI) process. The CAPRI process is similar to the VARTM process except that two vacuum pumps are used in the CAPRI process; one at the inlet side and one at the outlet side to create different vacuum levels [8]. By adjusting the pressure gradient to lower values than in the VARTM process, relaxation of the preform was minimized. Thus, a more uniform part thickness with a higher volume fraction is targeted in the CAPRI process.

Before infusion, the resin was degassed in a vacuum oven at 27°C for at least 30 minutes. The hybrid preform/tool assembly and the resin pot were preheated to 27°C prior to the infiltration in an air circulating oven. A thermocouple was attached to the surface of the vacuum bag to monitor the temperature. At the infiltration temperature, the resin viscosity was 0.516 Pa and the pressure at the injection port was set to 0.5 atm (50.66 kPa). During infiltration, the flow patterns on the top surface of the hybrid preform were recorded with a video camera. After infusion, the saturated hybrid preform was cured at 38°C for two hours and at 71°C for six hours.

4 Simulation Results

The results of the flow simulation for the conditions employed in the infiltration experiment are shown in Figures 5 and 6. The contour plots showing the simulation results were created by using the post-processor data imaging software TECPLOT. The color scale bar below the simulation results represents the volume fraction of the infiltrating fluid (phase 1). The color red represents a fluid volume fraction of 1, i.e. fully saturated. The color blue represents a fluid volume fraction of 0, i.e. completely dry. In Figure 5, the measured flow patterns on the top surface of the distribution medium (top), and the flow patterns predicted by the simulation model on the top surface of the distribution medium (center) and on the bottom surface of the hybrid preform (bottom) are shown at selected time frames. Overall, the model predicted shape and position of the flow fronts on the top surface of the distribution medium compared well with the measured values at the three selected times.

Fig. 5. The measured flow patterns on the top surface of the distribution medium (top), and the flow patterns predicted by the simulation model on the top surface of the distribution medium (center) and on the bottom surface of the hybrid preform (bottom) are shown at selected times during infiltration. Scale bar represents resin volume fraction in panel.

Fig. 6. The measured flow patterns on the top surface of the distribution medium (top), and the flow patterns predicted by the simulation model on the top surface of the distribution medium (center) and on the bottom surface of the hybrid preform (bottom) are shown at selected times during infiltration. Scale bar represents resin volume fraction in panel.

The measured flow patterns on the top surface of the distribution medium (top), and the flow patterns predicted by the simulation model on the top surface of the distribution medium (center) and on the bottom surface of the hybrid preform (bottom) are shown at two critical time periods in Figure 6. A comparison between the measured and predicted time to completely infiltrate the distribution medium is shown by the figures on the left side of Figure 6. The measured infiltration time of 4 minutes 25 seconds (left, top) compares well with the predicted time of 4 minutes (left, center). Almost no resin infiltration was predicted on the bottom surface of the hybrid preform (left, bottom) which is not unreasonable.

The time to completely infiltrate the hybrid preform was measured to be about an hour as shown in Figure 6. (right, top). At the same time period, the model predicts complete infiltration of both the top (see Figure 6, right, center) and bottom (see Figure 6, right, bottom) surfaces of the hybrid preform. The flow patterns and the infiltration times predicted by the simulation model of a CAPRI/FML process agreed quite well with the actual test measurements.

5 Conclusions

A simulation model of the VARTM/CAPRI FML infiltration process was developed using the CFD software package FLUENT. The three-dimensional model used the VOF two-phase resin-air model to track the flow patterns and the infiltration times at the top and bottom surfaces of the hybrid preform during the resin infusion stage of the VARTM and CAPRI manufacturing processes. The discrete resin pathways in the metal sheets were modeled as a series of parallel porous strips using the porous jump boundary condition in FLUENT. Use of the porous jump condition allowed creation of a simpler, more stable and robust model. The FLUENT simulation model was used to investigate the infiltration process during manufacture of a fiber metal laminate by the CAPRI process. The flow patterns and infiltration times predicted by the simulation model agreed quite well with the measurements obtained during manufacture of a FML panel.

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